

Metal Chelates of Some N-Acyl Hydroxamic Acids Containing Sulphonimido Group. Part. I : pH -Metric Study of the Complex Formation of Cu(II) with N(N'-Benzene Sulphonyl Glycyl) N-Phenyl Hydroxyl Amine

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pH -metric study of the reaction of Cu(II) with the ligand N(N'-benzenesulphonyl glycyl) N-phenyl hydroxyl amine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH_2CON(OH)C_6H_5$, indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal ligand complexes. Stepwise stability constants (K_1 and K_2) and successive acid dissociation constants (k_{2NH} and k_{1NH}) of the 1:2 complex have been determined by following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti. $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, pK_{2NH} and pK_{1NH} are found to be 8.19 ± 0.03 , 6.71 ± 0.03 , 10.30 ± 0.04 and 11.00 ± 0.04 respectively at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium at ionic strength 0.50 M (NaClO₄). The pK_a and pK_1 values of the ligand are 9.94 ± 0.03 and 11.72 ± 0.04 respectively under identical condition. Unusually small enhancement of acidity of the imido (-NH-) group on coordination to Cu(II) has been explained.

DURING the last four decades several N-acyl hydroxamic acids have been proved very useful for the determination of quite a large number of metal ions and separation of many difficulty separable mixtures¹. Incorporation of a sulphonimido (-SO₂NH-) group in suitable positions of acyl hydroxamic acids has produced an interesting series of chelating agents with one more donor site having some specificity for the metal ions of group IB and IIB²⁻⁵. The present communication describes the isolation and characterisation of the ligand, N(N'-benzenesulphonyl glycyl) N-phenylhydroxyl amine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH_2CON(OH)C_6H_5$ (or LH₂) and pH -metric study of its acid dissociation and complex formation with Cu(II) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium at a constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.50$ M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

The ligand N(N'-benzenesulphonyl glycyl) N-phenyl hydroxyl amine was obtained as a white solid on condensing N-benzenesulphonyl glycyl chloride with β -phenyl hydroxyl amine in aqueous solution in the presence of NaHCO₃, followed by neutralisation with dil. H₂SO₄ to $pH=4.0$. It was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol, dried in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H₂SO₄ and KOH (solid) and analysed. Found, m.p., 141-142°; C, 55.56; H, 5.01; N, 9.08%. Calc.

for $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH_2CON(OH)C_6H_5$: C, 54.90; H, 4.58 and N, 9.15%. IR (KBr)⁶: OH 3265(m), NH 3190(m), C=O 1635(s), -SO₂N < 1335(s), 1165(s), cm⁻¹ and UV: $\lambda_{max}^{Ethanol}$ 252 and 224 nm (log ϵ 4.07 and 3.97 respectively). All other reagents were either of A.R. quality or properly purified and their solutions were prepared in CO₂-free water and purified dioxan⁷.

pH -metric titrations of 50 ml solutions containing (i) 0.01(M) HClO₄, (ii) 0.01(M) HClO₄ + 0.01(M) LH₂, (iii) 0.01(M) HClO₄ + 0.01(M) LH₂ + 0.002(M) Cu(II), (iv) 0.01(M) HClO₄ + 0.01(M) LH₂ + 0.003(M) Cu(II)

were performed in 50% (v/v) water-dioxan medium with a standard solution of NaOH in the same solvent mixture while maintaining the ionic strength constant at $\mu=0.50$ (M) by adding requisite amount of NaClO₄.

pH -measurements were made with a Cambridge pH -meter (Portable type) using a glass electrode of 1-13 pH range and a saturated calomel electrode, connected to the cell by means of an agar-2(M) NaNO₃ bridge. The meter was calibrated with aqueous buffer solutions, e. g., 0.01(M) HClO₄, phthalate buffer and borate buffer solutions with appropriate temperature corrections.

Fig. 1. pH-titration Curves :

- Curve I : 0.01 (M) HClO₄
- .. II : 0.01 (M) HClO₄ + 0.01 (M) LH₂
- .. III : 0.01 (M) HClO₄ + 0.01 (M) LH₂ + 0.002 (M) Cu(II)
- .. IV : 0.01 (M) HClO₄ + 0.01 (M) LH₂ + 0.003 (M) Cu(II)

pH-titration curves, (pH vs. volume of standard NaOH solution) were drawn (Fig. 1) and the average coordination numbers (\bar{n} values) and free ligand concentrations were calculated by following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁸.

Results and Discussion

I. Stepwise Acid Dissociation of the Ligand, LH₂ :

Consumption of two equivalents of alkali per mole of the ligand, LH₂, in solution (ii) in the pH range 8.5 to 12.5 (Curve II, Fig. 1) indicated two steps of acid dissociation for LH₂ as represented by :

where k_1 and k_2 are the two successive proton-ligand (L²⁻) instability constants. The plot of \bar{n}_H (the average number of protons bound to the ligand ion, L²⁻) against pH (Curve I, Fig. 2) shows

Fig. 2. Complex formation Curves :

- Curve I : ○—○, \bar{n}_H (pH) plot for LH₂.
- .. II : \bar{n}_{LH} (pLH) plot for [Cu(LH)₂] :
- , 0.002 (M) Cu(II) ;
- , 0.003 (M) Cu(II).
- .. III : \bar{n}_H (pH) plot for [Cu(LH)₂] :
- , 0.002 (M) Cu(II) and
- , 0.003 (M) Cu(II).

$k_2/k_1 < 100$. The refined values of the constants were evaluated by the method of linear plots employing suitable forms of the function

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{\left(\frac{2[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} \right)}{\left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} + 1 \right)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The refined pk_2 and pk_1 values are stated in Table 1.

II. Complex formation of Cu(II) with LH₂ :

pH-titration curves of solutions (iii) and (iv) (Curves III and IV, Fig. 1) shows that two equivalents of acid per gm ion of Cu(II) were liberated in the pH range 3.0 to 7.0. From an analysis of the titration data in this pH range according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁸ it was found that one equivalent of acid per gm ion of Cu(II) was liberated for the association of each mole of the ligand species to the Cu(II) ion. Stepwise complex formation of Cu(II) with LH₂ has, therefore, been assumed to take place according to (4) and (5) :

where, K_1 and K_2 are the two successive formation constants. From the complex formation curves, \bar{n}_{LH} (pLH), (Curve II, Fig. 2) it appears that the steps (4) and (5) are overlapping (e.g., $K_1/K_2 < 100$). The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated by projection strip method^{9a} and finally refined by the method of linear plots using suitable forms of the function :

$$\bar{n}_{LH} = \frac{(K_1[LH] + 2K_1K_2[LH]^2)/(1 + K_1[LH] + K_1K_2[LH]^2)}{\dots} \quad (6)$$

The refined values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND Cu(II)-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT $30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ IN 50% (v/v) WATER-DIOXAN MEDIUM HAVING IONIC STRENGTH 0.50M (NaClO₄)

pK_2	pK_1	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	pK_2NH	pK_1NH
9.94	11.72	8.19	6.71	10.30	11.00
± 0.03	± 0.04	± 0.03	± 0.03	± 0.04	± 0.04

III. Acid dissociation of the Complex $[Cu(LH)_2]$:

Liberation of two further moles of acid from solutions (iii) and (iv) in the pH range from 9.0 to 12.1 (Curves III and IV, Fig. 1) i.e., after the association of two moles of the ligand ion, LH^- , per mole of copper, was accounted for by assuming stepwise deprotonation of the complex, $[Cu(LH)_2]$, evidently from the coordinated sulphonimido $-SO_2NH-$ groups :

where k_2NH and k_1NH are the two successive acid dissociation constants. The values of \bar{n}_h , the average number of protons bound to the complex ion $Cu(L)_2^{2-}$, were calculated assuming all the Cu(II) ion in the form of the 1 : 2 complex at pH values greater than 9.0. The \bar{n}_h (pH) plot, (Curve III, Fig. 2) shows that the steps (7) and (8) are overlapping (e.g., $k_2NH/k_1NH < 10$). Therefore, as in the case of K_1 and K_2 the constants k_2NH and k_1NH were also evaluated by projection strip method^{9a} and finally refined by the method of linear plots employing suitable forms of the function similar to (3) with \bar{n}_H , k_2 and k_1 replaced by \bar{n}_h , k_2NH and k_1NH respectively. The refined values of pK_2NH and pK_1NH are stated in Table 1.

Limits of error in the determination of the constants were found out as usual^{9b} and are stated in Table 1. Standard deviations^{9b} were found to be in the range $\pm 0.015 - \pm 0.025$.

Unlike the sulphonimides of the amino acids²⁻⁵ the enhancement of acidity of the imido ($-NH-$) group on coordination to a metal ion has been found to be small in the present case. X-ray study on the crystalline complex, $Cu(LH)_2 \cdot 2H_2O^{10}$ indicates that copper is coordinated through oxygens of the $-C-N-$ moiety in the basal plane of the

copper coordination sphere. These two observations suggest that the nitrogens (i.e., of the $-NH-$ group) most probably occupy the apical positions about copper and the smaller enhancement of acidity of the imido group reflect a Z-out John-Teller distortion, characteristic of Cu(II) and thereby weakening the Cu-N bonds,

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